

Community Knowledge and Perceptions of Estero el Salado, an Urban Protected Area in Puerto Vallarta, Jalisco, Mexico, and its Management

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Abstract

Urban protected areas are becoming valuable tools to conserve biodiversity in an urbanizing world. Local public support for urban protected areas is important for the successful conservation of them. In Puerto Vallarta, Mexico, Estero el Salado is an estuarine urban protected area surrounded by development. We engaged in a human dimensions study of Puerto Vallartan knowledge and perceptions of Estero el Salado as a measurement of support for its existence and continued conservation efforts. While there is generally strong support for the continued conservation of Estero el Salado, it is also unknown among a large portion of the city population, and an even smaller proportion of citizens have visited it. These two variables are very important in statistically higher support for conservation and the education roles of Estero el Salado. We recommend increased awareness and education campaigns with the city to maintain the desire for its conservation into the future.

Keywords: Urban protected areas, human dimensions, protected areas management, Mexico.

Topluluk Bilgisi ve Meksika'nın Jalisco Eyaletindeki Puerto Vallarta'da Bulunan Kentsel Koruma Alanı Estero el Salado ve Yönetimine İlişkin Algıları

Öz

Kentsel korunan alanlar, kentleşen bir dünyada biyolojik çeşitliliği korumak için değerli araçlar haline gelmiştir. Kentsel korunan alanlara yerel halkın desteği, bu alanların başarılı bir şekilde korunması için önemlidir. Meksika, Puerto Vallarta'da, Estero el Salado, gelişmelerle çevrili bir haliç kentsel korunan alanıdır. Puerto Vallarta'nın Estero el Salado hakkındaki bilgi ve algılarını, varlığına ve devam eden koruma çabalarına verilen desteğin bir ölçüsü olarak insan boyutlarında bir çalışma yürütülmüştür. Estero el Salado'nun devam eden korunmasına genel olarak güçlü bir destek olsa da, şehir nüfusunun büyük bir kısmı tarafından bilinmemektedir ve daha da küçük bir oranda vatandaş burayı ziyaret etmektedir. Bu iki değişken, Estero el Salado'nun korunmasına ve eğitim rollerine yönelik istatistiksel olarak daha yüksek destekte çok önemlidir. Gelecekte korunması arzusunu sürdürmek için şehirle birlikte farkındalığın ve eğitim kampanyalarının artırılması önerilmiştir.

Anahtar kelimeler: Kentsel korunan alanlar, insan boyutları, korunan alanların yönetimi, Meksika.

Citation: Malcolm, C. D. & Chávez Dagostino, R.M. (2025). Community knowledge and perceptions of Estero el Salado, an urban protected area in Puerto Vallarta, Jalisco, Mexico, and its management. *Journal of Protected Areas Research*, 4 (1), 43-56.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16731645>

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose

A protected area is defined by the International Union for the Conservation of Nature as “a clearly defined geographical space, recognised, dedicated and managed, through legal or other effective means, to achieve the long-term conservation of nature with associated ecosystem services and cultural values” (Dudley, 2008). It is generally accepted that protected areas are effective tools to conserve biodiversity (Rodrigues et al., 2004), although there remains a wide degree of variation in effectiveness (Kearney et al., 2020). The majority of globally protected areas are rural in their geography, and the classical protected area is generally portrayed as a rural entity. However, as our global population is becoming increasingly urbanized, the concept of urban protected areas has become more popular. There is a decided difference between a traditional, rural protected area and an urban protected area, which can be found in or at the edge of urban developments (Trzyna, 2014). They are, nevertheless, important tools for both conservation and ecotourism.

In Puerto Vallarta, Jalisco, Mexico, there exists an urban protected area, Estero el Salado, established and governed by the *Fideicomiso para la Protección del Estero el Salado y el Desarrollo de las Areas Colindantes*, a trust of the State of Jalisco. Estero el Salado is one of the only remaining natural riverine estuary environments on the Bay of Banderas. The purpose of this project is to assess knowledge of, as well as attitudes toward, Estero el Salado and its management among Puerto Vallartans. The results provide a lens through which we can measure the importance of this urban protected area and its conservation to residents of the city.

1.2. Urban Protected Areas

As of 2024, there are 302,934 protected areas and 6,464 OECMs (Other effective area-based conservation measures) in 247 countries across the globe, covering 17.6% of the Earth’s terrestrial and inland waters, and 8.4% of its marine habitat (UNEP-WCMC and IUCN, 2024). We can theorize that urban protected areas compose a minority of these numbers, given their more recent evolution, but urban protected areas possess no formal, separate recognition from rural protected areas, and there is no global inventory of urban protected areas (Trzyna, 2014). In this paper, we are not referring to urban parklands of grass and flowerbeds, with playgrounds for children, but the IUCN definition of a protected area within or near the edge of an urban area. Thus, they are set aside to protect biodiversity, allowing visitation and recreation, along with some education opportunities. They can provide ecosystem services, such as water filtration, and protect rare species of flora and fauna, but also provide tourism revenue for the local area (Olena et al., 2020). They can be classified using the IUCN Protected Area Management Categories and Governance Types (Dudley, 2008), although this must be considered in the decidedly anthropogenic context of an urban landscape. Phillips & Gay (2001), based on existing urban natural areas at the time, and McNeeley (2001), based on Phillips and Gay’s analysis, further provide categories that may be used to specifically classify protected areas: 1) heirloom urban protected areas, 2) urban refugia, 3) urban greenbelts, and 4) designed urban natural areas (McNeeley, 2001).

Cities can harbour hotspots of biodiversity (Knapp, Kuhn & Mosbrugger, 2008), so although urban protected areas can therefore often protect biodiversity, they are distinctive to rural protected areas in five main characteristics: 1) they offer the opportunity for a natural experience to large populations of nearby people and can consequently receive a great number of diverse, daily visitors, 2) they may be more visible to urban stakeholders such as city governmental managers, education and cultural organizations, and the media, 3) by nature of their location, they are more threatened by urban development, which leads to, 4) more crime, litter, light and noise pollution; however, they can also, 5) develop an appreciation for nature conservation among urban populations (Trzyna, 2014).

Due to their proximity to anthropogenic systems, the list of differences in the previous paragraph indicates that management of urban protected areas poses challenges that rural protected areas may not. In particular, urban areas are subject to dynamic urban land use changes that may conflict with protected area goals (De Leon & Kim, 2017), and may require specific research and management

attention (Conner, 2005) to deal with such issues as encroachment of urban landscape uses (Antos et al., 2007; Trzyna, 2014), such as the construction of building infrastructure and run-off of water contaminated with oils, detergents, and other toxins associated with urban landscapes, which can lead to negative impacts such as degradation and fragmentation of floral and faunal habitats (Hamilton et al., 2013) and concomitant disturbance and changes to wildlife behaviour (Leroux & Kerr, 2013; Ehrenfeld, 2000). In addition, socio-economic valuation of environments (Warren et al., 2011) (such as urban resident knowledge, opinions, and attitudes) and city land use policy (Thorne et al., 2013) can impact the effectiveness of urban protected areas.

Social science understanding related to protected areas is plentiful but is mainly restricted to rural protected areas in developing countries (although De Leon & Kim (2017) present some information on an urban protected area), who analysed local urban stakeholders concerning land changes but did not collect attitude and perception data from residents). Through this body of research it has been found that the majority of people have positive attitudes toward protected areas globally (Allendorf, 2020) and there is a well-founded theory that the positive support of local residents is important to the success of protected areas conservation (Holmes, 2013), although Brockington (2004) argues that lack of local support should not eliminate the effectiveness of protected areas, particularly in regions of rural poverty, where resistance may be weak. Research that has investigated this dichotomy of regional residential support versus opposition to protected areas is varied. For example, Kideghesho et al. (2007) found that locals demonstrated negative attitudes towards a local protected area in Tanzania, where requirements of pasturing and watering domestic animals were perceived to be limited by the presence of the park. Human-wildlife conflicts, particularly with large mammals, both herbivore and carnivore, also contribute to negative attitudes towards local protected areas (Hemson et al., 2009; Newmark et al., 1994; Ogra, 2008), which can undermine conservation goals (De Boer & Baquete, 1998). Acquah et al. (2017) found that although adjacent residents generally had positive attitudes towards Mole National Park, Ghana, there were negative attitudes towards issues of crop damage and loss of farmland. Programs such as the Communal Areas Management Programme for Indigenous Resources (CAMPFIRE) in Africa have been implemented to deal with these issues to varying degrees of success (Gandiwa et al., 2013). On the other hand, Mavah et al. (2018) demonstrated a positive correlation between proximity to a protected area in the Republic of Congo and access to essential bushmeat resources and hypothesized that the protected area served as a reservoir of wildlife important to villagers in the region. With respect to local tourism, particularly wildlife-based tourism in developing countries, locals can sometimes benefit, in the way of employment, or be negatively affected, such as the cases in which outside companies come to dominate the activities of protected area—oriented tourism (Nepal, 1997).

Understanding the meanings people ascribe to protected areas can influence their behaviours towards, and relationships with, them (Choe et al., 2024), meaning what people think is the purpose of a local protected area may influence their attitudes to, and relationship with it. We hypothesize that, particularly in the presence of urban development goals, Puerto Vallarta residents' understanding of and attitudes toward Estero el Salado may be important in current and future support for its conservation.

1.3. Estero el Salado

Estero el Salado is a small protected estuarine area within the city of Puerto Vallarta (Figure 1). It is administered by the *Fideicomiso para la Protección del Estero el Salado y el Desarrollo de las Areas Colindantes*, in trust by the government of the State of Jalisco in order to conserve the regional mangrove ecosystem, facilitate research activities, and offer educational activities for local inhabitants and tourists (Gobierno del Estado de Jalisco, 2000). The ecological conservation zone has an area just over 168 ha, 140 ha of which is covered by three species of mangrove, *Rhizophora mangle*, *Avicennia germinans*, and the dominant species, *Laguncularia racemosa* (Navarro-Rodriguez et al., 2019). A small upland area of the estuary exists at the northern end, upstream, and is composed of thorn forest, dominated by *Pithecellobium lanceolatum*, *P. dulce*, *Acacia hindsii*, and *A. micrantha*; this area is particularly threatened by human development and crops.

The Estero el Salado mangrove ecosystem is an important regional example of a natural coastal ecological zone that conserves various species of birds, mammals, reptiles, amphibians, and crustaceans, and provides significant ecosystem services. The ecosystem's health and biodiversity are currently maintained despite its location in an urbanized area, making it an important ecological "island" that provides wildlife habitat and supports ecological restoration efforts.

Despite being under urban pressure, Estero el Salado hosts a rich aquatic and terrestrial avian diversity, some of which reproduce in the estuary. Research conducted from 1996 to 1997 identified 28 species of waterbirds. These included 16 resident species, 11 winter residents, and one migratory species, highlighting the role as a feeding, resting, and nesting ground for both temporary and permanent avian populations (Cupul Magaña, 2000). These numbers were extended later to 160 water and terrestrial bird species, a diversity that surpasses that of other wetlands in the Bahía de Banderas region, highlighting the area's ecological significance (Molina et al., 2012). Habitat use of the mangrove by birds at Estero el Salado throughout the year has also been of interest, especially the endangered military macaw (*Ara militaris*) (Ornelas Carrillo et al., 2013).

There have been 29 species of mammal identified in the protected area, 69% of which are bats. Other mammals include common raccoon (*Procyon lotor*), Virginia opossum (*Didelphis virginiana*), nine-banded armadillo (*Dasypus novemcinctus*), and white-nosed coati (*Nasua narica*) (Guerrero et al., 2014). The estuary supports diverse crustacean populations, including *Macrobrachium tenellum* and the crab species *Uca latimanus* and *Cardisoma crassum* (De La Cruz-Manjarrez & Vázquez-López, 2015; Jáuregui-Velázquez & Bárcena-Gutiérrez, 2017; Molina-Ortega & Vázquez-López, 2018).

Other faunal inhabitants include 29 species of amphibians and reptiles, including the green iguana (*Iguana iguana*) and American crocodile (*Crocodylus acutus*). The crocodile is one of the most notable inhabitants of Estero el Salado, and has received regional research attention related to its biology, ecology, and habitat use (Cupul-Magaña, 2012; Nácar-Muñoz et al., 2016; Rubio-Miranda, 2018). Crocodylians are controversial species; on the one hand, the American crocodile is protected in Mexico, while at the same time, it is perceived as a threat, causing conflicts with humans (Cupul-Magaña et al., 2010). Feral fauna, primarily cats and dogs, is a conservation concern with respect to predation on native species in Estero el Salado (García-Padilla et al., 2014).

Figure 1. Location of Estero el Salado in Puerto Vallarta (van Heyst, 2025)

Estero el Salado has not been assessed an IUCN Protected Areas Management Category, but we hypothesize that it would be assessed at a Level IV, "Habitat or Species Management Area," which is characterized by management mainly for conservation through active management (Dudley, 2008), and further, an "Urban Refugia," as defined by McNeeley (2001). There is a small amount of ecotourism in the lower portion of the estuary, consisting of a boat tour partway up the estuarine river during which a guide explains about the mangroves and wildlife that is observed. The activities in the area are considered sustainable, but the cost of entry may exclude local people (Gallardo-Lara & Chávez-

Dagostino, 2019; Ortiz López et al., 2015). The Estero el Salado mangrove ecosystem provides critical ecosystem services, such as climate change mitigation, including carbon sequestration, that are also economically valued for their contribution to tourism. The willingness to pay for these services is estimated at USD 150 million annually (Figueroa et al., 2021), demonstrating the potential for implementing important conservation measures.

While the Estero el Salado mangrove ecosystem is currently thriving, it faces challenges from urbanization and climate change. The economic valuation of its ecosystem services underscores the importance of sustainable management and conservation efforts to ensure its continued ecological and economic benefits. However, this will require regional support for Estero el Salado in an urban setting where the continued development of tourism infrastructure is greatly valued.

2. Material and Methods

Questionnaires were administered anonymously throughout Puerto Vallarta by students from Centro Universitario de la Costa, in which the students asked four neighbours (one on each side of their house and two directly across the street) to participate. All students signed an oath of confidentiality with respect to any knowledge they gained while administering the surveys. Participation was limited to those 18 years of age and older. The questionnaire and its administration method were approved by the Brandon University Research Ethics Committee (Certificate #22371). A total of 325 questionnaires were obtained from 33 of the approximately 70 colonias throughout the city of Puerto Vallarta.

The questionnaire was administered in Spanish and primarily collected quantitative data in three sections: 1) demographics, 2) previous experience with Estero el Salado, 3) attitudes toward the management of Estero el Salado in the form of Likert items along a scale of “strongly disagree”, “disagree”, “neutral”, “agree”, or “strongly agree.” Quantitative items were analyzed using the Mann-Whitney U-test to assess differences between two independent groups and the Kruskal-Wallis test between three or more groups.

Lastly, we provided a qualitative, open-ended item in which respondents were invited to make voluntary comments about Estero el Salado. These responses were translated into English and examined using content analysis methods that recorded the use of key words and word repetition (Strauss & Corbin, 1998) to sort the responses into common expressions.

3. Findings and Discussion

Respondents to the questionnaire were 47.9% male and thus 52.1% female. The majority of respondents were in the 20-29 (35%), 30-39 (31.9%), and 40-49 (22.5%) age groups, and were moderately (secondary, 21.5%; preparatory, 33.3%) to highly educated (university, 35.6%). Only sixty-eight percent of the respondents indicated that they knew that Estero el Salado existed. Of those who knew about Estero el Salado (n=219), 34.2% had visited (23.1% of total, n=325). Of those that had visited (n=75), 74.3% had visited 1 to 2 times, 14.7% 3 to 4 times, and 10.7% 5 or more times. Of the participants that indicated they knew about Estero el Salado but had not visited (n=136), 54.4% responded yes, they planned to visit in the future, 38.2% stated maybe, and 7.4% indicated no, they did not plan to visit.

Of the respondents who indicated they knew about Estero el Salado (n=219), 54.8% stated they knew the purpose of the protected area. In 100% of these cases, an Active Management term was given for the question “What is the purpose of Estero el Salado?” such as “conserve” or “preserve” (Table 1). In 29% of the cases, a Geographical Active Management Target was given (Table 2), and in 61.8% of the cases, a Biological Active Management Target was given (Table 3). For example, in the response

“Protect nature,” “protect” is the Active Management term, and “nature” is a Geographical Active Management Target, while in the response “Conserve crocodiles,” “conserve” is the Active Management term, and “crocodiles” is a Biological Active Management Target. Approximately 10% only provided an Active Management term (e.g., “conserve”) without a target.

Table 1. Active management terms given for “What is the purpose of Estero el Salado?”

Action terms	n	%
Conserve/conservation	48	35.0
Preserve/preservation	43	31.6
Protect/protection	21	15.4
Take care of	18	13.2
Aware(ness)	4	2.9
Tourism	3	2.2
Environmental	2	1.5
Inform(ation)	1	0.7

Table 2. Geographical active management targets for “What is the purpose of Estero el Salado?”

Active management target: geographical	n	%
nature/natural	12	8.8
habitat	11	8.1
area(s)	5	3.7
ecosystem	3	2.2
environment	3	2.2
estuary	3	2.2
biodiversity	1	0.7
natural area	1	0.7
protected area	1	0.7

Table 3. Biological Active Management targets for “What is the purpose of Estero el Salado?”

Active management target: biological	n	%
species	38	27.9
crocodile(s)	25	18.4
animal(s)	18	13.2
fauna	17	12.5
flora	16	11.8
mangroves	8	5.9
bird(s)	6	4.4
wildlife	6	4.4
plant(s)	4	2.9
reptile(s)	4	2.9

In 33% of the cases in which a Biological Active Management Target was given, multiple targets were stated, e.g., “Preserve flora *and* fauna.”

We also asked the respondents if they knew who manages Estero el Salado. Only one person responded correctly that it is managed in trust by the State of Jalisco. Three percent of respondents answered “state government,” and 13.3% answered “government” in general, while 57.8% stated that they didn’t know.

Table 4 indicates the overall response rates for nine items regarding protection, education, and tourism at Estero el Salado.

Table 4. Overall response rates (%) for the importance of protection, education, and tourism statements at Estero el Salado.

Statement	Not at all important	Somewhat important	Important	Extremely important
How important do you think it is to preserve areas like Estero el Salado?	0.9	8.1	37.6	53.4
How important do you think Estero el Salado is for tourism in Puerto Vallarta?	3.4	21.1	48.1	27.3
How important is it to develop Estero el Salado for more tourism?	5.0	19.6	47.2	28.3
How important do you think Estero el Salado is for education?	2.5	15	43.8	38.8
How important do you think it is to have protected areas like Estero el Salado inside Puerto Vallarta?	0	8.4	30.6	60.9
How important is it to conserve crocodiles in Estero el Salado?	2.5	12.9	30.5	54.1
How important is it to understand habitat use by birds and fish in Estero el Salado?	0.6	9.0	31.2	59.2
How important is it to conserve mangrove trees in Estero el Salado?	0	5.9	28.7	65.1
How important is it to have school tours to Estero el Salado?	5.6	15.0	44.9	34.3
How important is it to have tourism tours in Estero el Salado?	4.4	23.4	28.3	34.0

Table 5 reports the response rates for the nine importance items for those respondents who reported they knew about Estero el Salado versus those that reported that they did not.

Table 5. Response rates (%) for importance of protection, education, and tourism statements at Estero el Salado for those who know about Estero el Salado (n= 218) and those who do not (n=103). Statistically significant differences are shown in bold.

Statement	Know of Estero el Salado	Not at all important	Somewhat important	Important	Extremely important	Mann-Whitney U-test, p-value
How important do you think it is to preserve areas like Estero el Salado?	Yes	0.5	5.5	32.1	61.9	0.000
	No	1.9	13.6	49.5	35	
How important do you think Estero el Salado is for tourism in Puerto Vallarta?	Yes	4.1	16.1	49.5	30.3	0.018
	No	1.9	31.1	45.6	21.4	
How important is it to develop Estero el Salado for more tourism?	Yes	6.4	16.1	46.8	30.7	0.195
	No	1.9	26.2	48.5	23.3	
How important do you think Estero el Salado is for education?	Yes	2.8	11.1	38.7	47.5	0.000
	No	2	23.5	53.9	20.6	
How important do you think it is to have protected areas like Estero el Salado inside Puerto Vallarta?	Yes	0	6.5	27.6	65.9	0.000
	No	0	11.8	37.3	51	
How important is it to conserve crocodiles in Estero el Salado?	Yes	3.7	10.7	27	58.6	0.050
	No	0	17.6	37.3	45.1	
How important is it to understand habitat use by birds and fish in Estero el Salado?	Yes	0	7.8	32.1	60.1	0.487
	No	2	10.8	29.4	57.8	

How important is it to conserve mangrove trees in Estero el Salado?	Yes	0	4.1	24.9	71	0.001
	No	0	9.7	36.9	53.4	
How important is it to have school tours to Estero el Salado?	Yes	5	14.7	44	36.2	0.367
	No	5.9	15.7	47.1	30.4	
How important is it to have tourism tours in Estero el Salado?	Yes	3.7	25.3	36.9	34.1	0.698
	No	4.9	19.4	41.7	34	

Table 6 reports the response rates for the nine importance items for those respondents who had visited Estero el Salado versus those who reported that they had not.

Table 6. Response rates (%) for the importance of protection, education, and tourism statements at Estero el Salado for those who had visited Estero el Salado (n= 218) and those who had not (n=103). Statistically significant differences are shown in bold

Statements	Visited Estero el Salado	Not at all important	Somewhat important	Important	Extremely important	Mann-Whitney U-test, p-value
How important do you think it is to preserve areas like Estero el Salado?	Yes	0	6.7	29.3	64	0.036*
	No	1.2	8.5	40.2	50	
How important do you think Estero el Salado is for tourism in Puerto Vallarta?	Yes	1.3	14.7	53.3	30.7	0.100
	No	4.1	23.2	46.3	26.4	
How important is it to develop Estero el Salado for more tourism?	Yes	4	17.3	44	34.7	0.186
	No	5.3	20.3	48	26.4	
How important do you think Estero el Salado is for education?	Yes	1.4	8.1	29.7	60.8	0.000
	No	2.9	17.1	47.8	32.2	
How important do you think it is to have protected areas like Estero el Salado inside Puerto Vallarta?	Yes	0	8	28	64	0.539
	No	0	8.6	31.6	59.8	
How important is it to conserve crocodiles in Estero el Salado?	Yes	5.5	11	24.7	58.9	0.569
	No	1.6	13.5	32	52.9	
How important is it to understand habitat use by birds and fish in Estero el Salado?	Yes	0	12	24	64	0.516
	No	0.8	8.2	33.1	58	
How important is it to conserve mangrove trees in Estero el Salado?	Yes	0	2.7	28	69.3	0.332
	No	0	6.9	28.6	64.5	
How important is it to have school tours to Estero el Salado?	Yes	6.7	12	38.7	42.7	0.168
	No	5.3	15.9	46.5	31.8	
How important is it to have tourism tours in Estero el Salado?	Yes	5.3	22.7	34.7	37.3	0.720
	No	4.1	23.7	39.2	33.1	

Table 7 lists the top five themes from the open-ended question “Do you have anything else you would like to say about Estero el Salado?” In total, there were 143 responses to this question.

Table 7. Top five themes and example comments for “Do you have anything else you would like to say about Estero el Salado?”

Theme	%
1. Need for protection of Estero el Salado “It is an extremely important place for its wildlife” “We have to take care of it” “It is a vital area for the ecosystem of Puerto Vallarta”	41.9
2. Importance of public awareness of Estero el Salado “Needs more promotion” “It has very little publicity” “You have to promote more to know about the estuary” “Projects like this are important to educate the Vallartans”	13.9
3. Perception of lack of care of Estero el Salado “Lacks care, make it more attractive...” “It is not very well taken care of, they do not show interest” “To me it seems abandoned or poorly attended to”	8.1
4. Estero el Salado is aesthetically pleasing “It is pretty” “I like it very much” “It is very big and very pretty”	7.0
5. Contain the crocodiles in Estero el Salado “As long as the crocodiles do not go out” “That the crocodiles be enclosed to be keep the people of Puerto Vallarta safe”	3.5

There are a number of important conclusions that we can form from these data concerning community knowledge, perceptions, and attitudes towards Estero el Salado and its management. First, knowledge of the existence Estero el Salado area is extremely important. Thirty-two percent of the respondents did not know that Estero el Salado exists in their city. Those who knew about Estero el Salado were statistically more likely to support its preservation. This is reflected in the open-ended question responses that there needs to be more knowledge and promotion of Estero el Salado. This also factors into the lack of knowledge and promotion of Estero el Salado in Puerto Vallarta. Only 54.8% of those who reported they knew about Estero el Salado stated that they also knew the purpose of the protected area. Again, this points toward a lack of knowledge about Estero el Salado on the part of Puerto Vallartans. A lack of knowledge of the protected area may lead to less support in the urban population in general, as suggested by Holmes (2013). There needs to be more public awareness efforts made on the part of the trust, *Fideicomiso para la Protección del Estero el Salado y el Desarrollo de las Areas Colindantes*, responsible for the conservation of Estero el Salado, to develop a proud feeling on the part of Puerto Vallartans for this protected area. Second, having visited Estero el Salado was also important. Only 34.2% of those who stated they knew about Estero el Salado (23.1% of all respondents) reported that they had visited Estero el Salado; these respondents also reported statistically greater support for its preservation. This low percentage in visitation may be due in part to the cost of entry, as mentioned by Gallardo-Lara & Chávez-Dagostino (2019) and Ortiz López et al. (2015).

Knowledge of, and visitation to, Estero el Salado is likely related to knowing the purpose of the protected area. We received a variety of responses to “What is the purpose of Estero el Salado?” but the answers could be grouped as follows: 100% of the participants that stated they knew the purpose of Estero el Salado responded to this question with an Action term such as “protect” or “conserve”. Approximately one-quarter of the respondents then added a Geographical Active Management Target such as “nature,” “ecosystem,” or “protected area,” while about 60% added a Biological Active Management Target such as “species,” or “crocodiles.” Therefore, more people identified the conservation purpose of Estero el Salado to be small-scale goals of a particular species, more akin to a zoo, while fewer identified the large-scale, holistic purpose of protecting an entire ecosystem as habitat for these species (i.e., with a Geographic Action Management Target). This result serves the message of Choe et al. (2024). Understanding and awareness of conservation at the biodiversity scale has been proven to

be crucial for protected areas success (Ibrahim, Assim, Johari, Mohammad. Afandi & Hassan, 2023), meaning the public needs to understand the purpose of a protected area at a broader level than a single species, such as crocodiles. Further, Scholte, van Teeffelen & Verburg (2015) found that a lack of understanding regarding ecological concepts, such as those espoused through ecosystem scale rather than species scale, can lead to challenges in environmental conservation. For example, if people think that Estero el Salado is solely for the protection of crocodiles, but they don't like crocodiles, there may be less support for the conservation of the protected area ecosystem as a whole. Given the high biodiversity and critical habitat for numerous taxa in Estero el Salado, this is an important item related to education messaging on the part of the trust, which should develop programs to educate regarding the role and purpose of protected area conservation.

Third, preservation of Estero el Salado, its habitat, and species was seen as more important than its role in education and tourism. However, the importance of education was statistically much more important to those who had visited Estero el Salado versus those who had not. It is therefore evident that knowing about and visiting Estero el Salado results in greater importance placed on the conservation, tourism, and particularly education goals of the protected area. A greater city-wide knowledge and education message about Estero el Salado within the community of Puerto Vallarta, such as in schools, or the establishment of an "Estero el Salado Celebration," including free admission for local residents, could strengthen these perceptions.

The open-ended question, "Do you have anything else to say about Estero el Salado," elicited many different responses, but there were several themes that were most common. The feeling of a need to continue to protect Estero el Salado was very strong among the respondents. This is a positive result. However, there was also a feeling that there needs to be more public awareness of Estero el Salado. We think this is also an important result as a greater knowledge and understanding of Estero el Salado within Puerto Vallarta should increase community desire for continued protection of the protected area (*sensu* Holmes, 2013; Ibrahim et al., 2023). A small percentage of respondents also indicated that they perceived the area is not well taken care of. This may be due to the view that people receive driving by: a high metal fence with mainly dirt and a few trees within. It seems unused and inaccessible to the public. One cannot see the beautiful river and mangrove forest within.

4. Conclusion and Suggestions

Upon receipt of a report of this research by the trust, a large, permanent, stonework sign is being erected at the entrance to Estero el Salado, and the parking lot, previously dirt, was laid with interlocking brick. This may help in fostering an improved knowledge about, and support for, Estero el Salado, an important, unique, and biodiverse urban protected area, surrounded and potentially threatened by continuing development of urban infrastructure such as housing, roads, and inflow of raw sewage due to a burst pipe, as happened in 2019. We also feel that some more development as a tourism destination in the city would protect it from urban threats, as it would be seen as a positive economic generator. Overall, the Estero el Salado appears to maintain ecological integrity, however, it will require continued vigilance on the part of the *Fideicomiso para la Protección del Estero el Salado y el Desarrollo de las Areas Colindantes* to keep it so into the future. It is obvious that although there is public support for its conservation, a wider understanding of the existence and purpose of Estero el Salado is warranted.

Acknowledgments and Information Note

The authors would like to thank all the participants who completed questionnaires for this project. Logistics of cooperation between the authors were made possible by the *Agreement for International Education Cooperation between Universidad De Guadalajara (Guadalajara, Mexico) and Brandon University (Brandon, Manitoba, Canada)*.

The article complies with national and international research and publication ethics, through the Brandon University Research Ethics Committee, Certificate #22371, January 4, 2019, to January 4, 2024.

Author Contribution and Conflict of Interest Disclosure Information

All authors contributed equally to the article. There is no conflict of interest.

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